

WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

As an entrepreneur, male-dominated industry also plays a role in shaping women entrepreneurs' understanding of glass ceiling. Respondent 08's business was in technology and she sees that men are less likely to take her seriously. Owning a business in the coffee industry, where it is often perceived as a masculine hobby, Respondent 04 entrepreneur experienced different types of barriers compared to her man counterparts. She said that building trust as a woman business owner in a male dominated industry is harder. Also, she also finds dealing with many stakeholders, such as farmers or merchants who is more likely to be men more difficult, therefore she sees these barriers as her glass ceiling in expanding her business. After analysing the data from the interviews, glass ceiling does have an impact on women entrepreneur, specifically on how they carry themselves and how they manage their business. Their glass ceiling exposure is proven to have affected how they see themselves, as woman and entrepreneur, how they create policies and make decision for their business.

Keywords: Entrepreneurs; Women. Family; Business; Indonesia.

1. Introduction

In the modern age of today, working women are not seen as something out of place. Although motivation of entering the labor force may vary, women are getting more visible in the workplace, whether in contemporary or in a more traditional setting (see Figure 1.1). Globally, women account for up to 40% of the total labor force (The World Bank, 2018). Similar finding is also found by Pew Research Center, where the median data on women in the workforce falls on 45,4% globally (Fetterolf, 2017). These women are mostly in the productive age and mostly single women who have never been married. Depending on the state of the country, many women can be found on the agriculture or services sector. Many of these women also contributes in the informal economy, especially in developing countries. Also, many women contribute in family and implicitly bring productivity to the economy, but labeled as unpaid activities, therefore sometimes excluded from the concept of productivity and economic contribution (Ferrant, Pesando, & Nowacka, 2014). Unpaid activities include taking care of the family, such as preparing meals, caring for children, or maintaining household.

Figure 1. Ratio of female to male labor force participation rates.

Source: The World Bank (2016)

Many of positive contributions from women to society comes from the increasing rate of 'attention' put in women empowerment. Many scholarly findings have found that empowering women means empowering society in general. After the Second World War ends, education for women started to boom, resulting in massive increase of professionally-trained women entering the workforce, therefore contributing positive input in the economy. According to OECD Report (2012), educating women and girls resulted in 50% of economic growth in the span of 50 years. Another possible explanation to the increase supply of women in the labor force is the introduction of contraception and family planning education. Revenga & Shetty (2012) stated that improvement of women's participation in the labor force in Bangladesh, Colombia, and Iran are due to better female education and fertility reduction.

In the case of Indonesia, working women is also commonly found in day to day activities and the stigma surrounding the topic has long subdued. According to a report by Ministry of Women Empowerment and Child Protection (2013), women make up 49.65% of Indonesia's population and represented in the labor force by 47,91%. The report also stated that 90,64% percent of female aged 15 years and older are well- literate, but education remains varied. Urban women are found to be more educated than the rural women counterparts. In politics, women hold 18% of total seats in the parliament (Bachelet, 2012). Indonesia has had one female president, Megawati Soekarnoputri, in the year of 2001 to 2004. In the current cabinet of ministers in Indonesia, Cabinet of Work 2018, women occupy eight spots in diverse fields, such as Sri Mulyani Indrawati (Minister of Finance), Siti Nurbaya Bakar (Minister of Environment and Forestry) and a public favorite, Susi Pudjiastuti (Minister of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries).

With the significance participation of women in the workplace, it is important to make sure that women are given equal opportunity and space to further grow and develop. Although women are proven to give positive contributions, there are still many challenges that women face daily in the workplace. The three challenges that will be highlighted here are prejudice, wage gap, and discrimination.

Prejudices about women is a common running theme when talking about women challenges in the workplace. Currently, no country in the world is considered one hundred percent gender equal. Many countries still have an element of patriarchal beliefs and culture, which led to prejudices about women that might prevent women from growth. In Indonesia especially, traditional gender roles are seen as practical norms which women should comply

and undergo in their lives. Patriarchy also runs deep in the country. Indonesia currently sits 84th out of 144 countries in terms of gender equality (Schwab, Samans, Zahiri et al., 2017).

In Indonesia, workplace harassment is not a popular topic that is more likely to go unreported. Although there are laws and regulations, execution in companies are often done loosely and many has not benefit the protection of the legislation. There is no official data on sexual harassment in the workplace in Indonesia, but according to Schanel & Das (2016), 99.2% of women factory workers in Indonesia expressed high rates of worry concerning job safety, sexual harassment, and verbal abuse in the workplace.

According to Parker & Funk (2017), 42% of US women admitted that they have experienced workplace discrimination (see Figure 1.4) in a diverse range of ways. The statistics worsen when the subject is minority women. Although majority women do not have it easy either, minority women are found to be harassed twice as much as majority women (Berdahl & Moore, 2006). Combining the data with the fact that women are often put in lower-paying position, this setting does not yield any good outcomes for hiring company (Bac, 2017). Women discrimination in the workplace is the last challenge that will be discussed in this chapter and will be the transitioning topic to the problem statement of the research. Discrimination is generally defined as an unfair treatment based on categories, either based on race, gender, or other attributes. For women, discrimination in the workplace can range between pay, treatment, and opportunity to grow.

Figure 2. Harassment in the workplace

Source: Parker & Funk (2017)

As highlighted in the beginning of this section, productive women are highly contributive in the society. In a discriminating society, many researchers have found that not only it is unethical, but it is also costly (see Figure 1.5). By minimizing the opportunity and discriminating women, society as a whole. According to Ferrant & Kolev (2016), gender discrimination in institutions is costing the global economy with up to twelve trillion US dollar. The

report stated that the current global gender discrimination is caused by many things, such as discriminatory laws and regulation, traditional gender norms, gender stereotypes, women restriction to proper education and labor, also mindsets that deny women empowerments.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Entrepreneurship

The topic of entrepreneurship has gained more popularity in the last five years due to the growing trend of tech startups as a career path. The success stories of many entrepreneurs have made a lot of people interested to enter the field with the hope of the similar success. According to Eisenmann (2013), the word entrepreneurship is often loosely attached to keywords like 'business', 'startups', and 'ventures'. In his article, Eisenmann also cited Howard Stevenson, a Harvard Business School professor's definition of entrepreneurship. Here, entrepreneurship is defined as "the pursuit of opportunity beyond resources controlled" (ibid.). Another definition by Gartner (1988) defined that entrepreneurship is simply "creation of organizations". According to The Global Entrepreneurship Index Report (2018), the field of entrepreneurship keeps growing with 3% increase globally, with 22% increase in product innovation and 11% increase in startup skills.

Another research done to study the important traits of entrepreneurs are also done by Cross & Travaglione (2003), showing the importance of emotional intelligence in becoming an entrepreneur. Emotional intelligence, often called EQ, is defined as the ability to understand and manage emotion, both coming from the self and other people. The research used two models developed by Mayer, Caruso, and Salovey (1999) and Goleman (1998). The first model explores emotional intelligence through emotion management skills and ability, while the second model examines emotional intelligence through five dimension of self awareness, self regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. In the research, it is shown that entrepreneurs scored high in emotional intelligence through both models, therefore concluded that entrepreneurs need high level of emotional intelligence to succeed in the venture.

2.2 Women Entrepreneurs in Indonesia

In Indonesia, women are also seen as a major key player for economic growth, due to the large number of women-owned MSMEs, or Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. According to The World Bank's research report of Women Entrepreneurs in Indonesia (2016), up to sixty of MSMEs are owned by women. Since most of the women entrepreneurs are tackling smaller-sized enterprises, the range of industry has been very diverse. With all the women population in Indonesia, almost 26% are considered active entrepreneurs, approximately around 22 million women. The average age of women entrepreneurs in Indonesia is 41-60 years old, mostly married with a high school degree for education qualification (see Figure 2.2). Although most do not own a university degree, women entrepreneurs in Indonesia is considered experienced and have the ability to run a business to generate decent amount of profit.

The existence of traditional gender roles in Indonesia do create a dilemma for productive, working women. The gender norms in Indonesia is very traditional, in a sense that women only work to support their husbands and their family, putting economic motives in the first place. It is not much of a self-achievement or a form of success, since it is believed that the women's place is at home to take care of the family. This conditions put heavier burden for Indonesian women than their Western counterparts. In a thesis by Cassandra (2017), third president of Indonesia, Soeharto has known to push ibuism agenda to put women in their place of being 'dutiful' to both husband and the country, creating generations-worth of gender segregation and inequality normalization. This pattern of serving the family first and putting careers aside also reflected in Asian countries, like Japan. In Japan, women often quit their job after they marry to bore children, but eventually will rejoin the labor market after the child is grown (Statistics Bureau of Japan, 2016). A similar pattern has also been found in Indonesia.

2.3 Opportunities and Challenges of Women Entrepreneurs

Women entrepreneurs are multidimensional in terms of opportunities and challenges, since what can be seen as opportunity may be a challenge to others and vice versa. Country, culture, gender roles, and the type of pattern of women entrepreneur choose may create different output for each cases.

De Vita, Mari, & Poggesi (2014) stated that in developing countries, women may find their role as an entrepreneur bring advantages in terms of loans and microcredit programs due to their important role and their 'effort' of gaining emancipation in the society. As barrier-breakers, women entrepreneurs in developing countries that has established proven business efficiency and gained trust from their stakeholders are more likely to get international funding than their male counterparts. However, research in South Asia also showed that women are

less likely to get credit than men by 3% (Wellalage & Locke, 2017). This is likely to happen due to the shortage of women in the funding industry, such as venture capitals or angel investors. According to Weisul (2016), female CEOs are only getting 2.7% of overall funding from venture capital, when companies with women founders outperforms those with all male founders by 63%. This phenomenon of women entrepreneurs' difficulties to get necessary funding for their business is called 'a second glass ceiling' for women, which will be further explored in the second part of the literature review.

As for opportunities, being born in an entrepreneurial family is a definite one for women entrepreneurs. As stated in the previous discussion, having a strong support system is helpful for women to enter and stay in the entrepreneurship ventures. Langowitz & Minniti (2007) also stated that the more entrepreneurs a woman know, the more likely she is to be confident to start her new business. A study done by Nikina, Shelton, & LeLoarne (2015) about role of spouse support in the success of women entrepreneur also shows that spouse support for married women entrepreneurs are not interchangeable and important. Supportive spouses that understand the dynamics of entrepreneurship will benefit women entrepreneurs in the long run, which seems fitting since many women entrepreneurs enter the venture as an option of conventional, corporate career or to seek a better balance for their role at home and at the office. A research done by McKay (2001) found that women entrepreneurs that do not have spouses find a greater flexibility and freedom of running the 'double role', but lack emotional and moral supporter.

The increasing conversation and awareness for gender equality and inclusivity may also become an opportunity for women entrepreneurs. More people are becoming more aware of the impact of women in general, supporting women that are currently taking business or entrepreneurial ventures. Stories of successful women entrepreneur has motivated more women to participate and creating their own business, creating a better ecosystem for both newcomers and old players (Reynolds, 2017). The European Commission also issued a statement that "female creativity and entrepreneurial potential are an underexploited source of economic growth and jobs that should be further developed" ("Female entrepreneurs", 2018).

2.4 Glass Ceiling

The term 'glass ceiling' is coined by Marilyn Loden, an American HR and management consultant in 1978 to shed light at the discrimination that many women has experienced in the workplace and how it limits women participation in leading the top-middle management positions. In her article in BBC news, Loden (2017) stated that although progress is visible, gender inequality in the workplace has been too normalized that many refuse to acknowledge that glass ceiling exists. Although women's participation in the labor force is increasing, the amount of women leading at the top remains stunted. In a Deloitte (2017) report, women only hold 15% of board seats globally. Although it was a 3% increase than the data founded in 2015, development is still regarded as sluggish.

According to Cotter, Hermsen, Ovardia, & Vanneman (2001), glass ceiling is defined as 'a specific type of gender or racial inequality that can be distinguished from other types of inequality'. In the study, glass ceilings may exist if it fulfils either four employment attributes in the job: if the inequality is unexplainable by other job-relevant qualities, if it is more often seen in more sophisticated level and roles than the smaller ones, if the inequality exists in the chances of advancing forward and not just about proportions, and if the chances decreases as the career grows. A study done by Veale & Gold (1998) revealed that women are a victim of heavy prejudice in the workplace. Women professional's career development are not as well supported and planned as their male counterparts, received less trainings and development opportunities, perceived as a threat by their male counterparts, and discriminated if the gender roles collide, such as being pregnant during the job.

Not only discrimination in participation, many scholars has brought the topic of equal pay to the glass ceiling table. It is believed that women Equal pay has been a popular topic from the early working women's movement. In his research, Edgeworth (1922) argued for both sides of the 'equal pay for equal work' statement, taking dependent, family size, and competition to account. Fortin, Bell, & Böhm (2017) study revealed that women's underrepresentation in the top level management have significant effect to the wage gap, putting women's lack of participation in the top level income as one of the proof of slow wage gap progress. Again, gender roles play a part in wage gap. The traditional gender role of men as breadwinners has create a culture that men deserves more compensation than women. According to Eagly & Carli (2007), men earn more when faced with marriage and parenthood, but the same understanding does not apply to women, creating a wider gap between women's and men's wage. Veale & Gold (1998) also stated that a woman manager found out that she was paid less than the male manager that previously held the job.

2.5 Research Framework

Figure 3. Research Framework

From the literature, it is possible to see that glass ceiling is a result of traditional gender roles, gender stereotype, and male-dominated environment of industry. Glass ceiling, along with other hygiene factor such as discrimination and harassment can push women to become women entrepreneurs. However, motivation factor such as the flexibility of balancing the double role and self-actualization for women may also affects women participation in entrepreneurship. These factors may influence women, and depending on the factors, can create two kinds of women entrepreneurs: corporate climbers or intentional entrepreneurs. The literature also shows that there is a possibility for women entrepreneurs to experience a glass ceiling outside the corporate ladder, in the form of difficulties garnering resources to start the business, lack of women in mentorship, and a similar pattern of discrimination due to the male-dominated nature of entrepreneur world in general.

3. Methodology

Due to the nature of this research, a qualitative exploratory study methodology was used to gain understanding on how glass ceiling 'motivates' women entrepreneurs to leave their previous job they had and start their own ventures. Exploratory study aims to further clarify the understanding of a problem or an event (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2008). This research design was aimed to explore the complexities of women entrepreneurs in Indonesia and their relationship with glass ceiling. First, this research touched on how glass ceiling is perceived by Indonesian women entrepreneur. Second, this research was aimed to explain the impact of glass ceiling on women entrepreneur's approaches and style of leadership.

For this research, the researcher used non-probability sampling with purposive or judgmental sampling. This technique is chosen due to the boundaries of the research. By using purposive sampling, the researcher will be sure that the respondents have the necessary requirements, experience, and understanding to fulfill the research objectives. To minimize bias and further explore the research objective, a heterogeneous or maximum variation sampling will be conducted to achieve diverse and unique data from the respondents (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2008).

This research had ten women entrepreneur with active and profitable businesses in the Jabodetabek area from different field and industry. This is to ensure that the answer will represent a diverse range of industry (Nath, 2000). A small sample of ten women entrepreneur is also chosen after examining other studies with similar research topics and the researcher remains guided (Jamali, 2009; Liu, 2013). Due to the budget limitation, only women entrepreneurs around Jabodetabek area will be chosen to support the data collection method of face-to-face interview. These women entrepreneurs will undergo a pre-check to ensure that they understand the concept of glass ceiling and have an opinion about it, either stories of experiences. Since the concept of glass ceiling is not yet developed in Indonesia, the researcher had to do a short presentation on the research and gave leads on the

definition of glass ceiling prior to starting the interview. Glass ceiling here is defined as limitation to succeed in a corporate career, and may include feeling of boredom, discomfort of working in a hostile, masculine-dominated business culture, and dissatisfaction of career development (Orhan & Scott, 2001).

Due to the objectives of the research, data are analyzed in a thematic data analysis. Thematic data analysis is defined as “a systematic approach to the analysis of qualitative data that involves identifying themes or patterns of cultural meaning” (Lapadat, 2010). Thematic data analysis in an inductive research also allows the flexibility to gain deeper information (ibid.). Thematic analysis starts by creating codes from the interview result and establish descriptive themes and looking for data saturation. From the data saturation, the researcher will develop themes, conclude the findings from the information, and preserve context (Thomas & Harden, 2006).

4. Result and Analysis

Qualitative research data was collected from sample of ten women entrepreneurs. Most of them have experienced glass ceiling in one form or another. All of them had prior formal work experience before starting their own business. The age ranges from early 20s to early 50s, with the majority ethnicity of Javanese and Islam as their religions. All of them have university education, ranging from associate’s degree (D3 in Indonesia) to master’s degree (S2 in Indonesia). Several of them have also been educated abroad. The women entrepreneurs have varied background and industry experience, most of them own businesses which are young and in existence about five years or less.

After coding the data through NVivo, there are five major themes that emerge. These themes areas will be discussed in details in this chapter: (i) women’s motivation to start a business, (ii) women entrepreneurs have an expanded definition of glass ceiling, (iii) glass ceiling has an impact on women entrepreneurs, (iv) the relationship between culture and glass ceilings, and (v) the importance of support for women entrepreneurs.

4.1 Women’s Motivation to Start a Business

When asked why they start their business, Indonesian women entrepreneurs answered with many different reasons, from retirement plan to self-actualization reasons. Out of ten women entrepreneurs, only two stated that experiencing glass ceiling motivates them to start a business and only one matches the identification of a ‘corporate climber’, but it still did not act as the main reason to start their own business. The data shows that the majority of Indonesian women entrepreneur did not enter entrepreneurship because they face glass ceiling in the workplace.

The majority of the data showed that women entrepreneurs start their business because their traditional gender roles were conflicting with their career options. There are three women that have to quit their previous jobs to take care of the family. To conclude, the majority of Indonesian women entrepreneurs starts their business as a way to serve the gender roles they are expected to, while still being productive and creative as themselves.

“So after I resigned from Bank CCC due to glass ceiling reasons, it turns out that my husband has the same vision of resigning and starting a business. So my husband and I ended up resigning from our jobs and we start our business together.” – Respondent 08

“I think the first thing was passion, because basically I love to sell things. Second, it was actually the glass ceiling. I think as a woman, our place... Well, even though it is not clearly written, but my family said that we are women. Why should I work in an office, or have a career, when I will end up getting married?” – Respondent 03

4.2 Women Entrepreneurs Have an Expanded Understanding of Glass Ceiling

Based on the findings done from the interview of ten women entrepreneurs in Jabodetabek area, women entrepreneurs see glass ceiling in a broad way. However, these women entrepreneurs are expressing that they face glass ceiling due to many different reason, including themselves, the people around them, and their gender roles, traditionally as a mother or a wife. The findings of this research also extends the understanding of the glass ceiling by women entrepreneurs since many women entrepreneurs agree that they still experience glass ceiling as an entrepreneur.

“Glass ceiling is... I see it as a barrier, from me personally, a barrier that is created by the women themselves. They are not breaking the glass ceiling because of the environment. I feel that we, Indonesian women, created so many ‘women excuses’ as a barrier for ourselves. For example, “But I am somebody’s wife” “But I have a child” “But I am” “But I have”. It means that the glass ceiling is there because you allow it to happen” – Respondent 07

“Glass ceiling, especially for women, I think it will exist, and it will never disappear. I think it goes back on who is your boss. I think the one that decide whether glass ceiling is exist or not in your career is your boss. I think your boss acts as the first filter whether you have glass ceiling or not in the office.” – Respondent 08

“The glass ceiling in Indonesia, the invisible barrier that myself felt also, is even though we work and we have a career, but as a wife, we have to have effort and attention to take care of the house and the children.” – Respondent 09

As an entrepreneur, male-dominated industry also plays a role in shaping women entrepreneurs’ understanding of glass ceiling. Respondent 08’s business was in technology and she sees that men are less likely to take her seriously. Owning a business in the coffee industry, where it is often perceived as a masculine hobby, Respondent 04 entrepreneur experienced different types of barriers compared to her man counterparts. She said that building trust as a woman business owner in a male dominated industry is harder. Also, she also finds dealing with many stakeholders, such as farmers or merchants who is more likely to be men more difficult, therefore she sees these barriers as her glass ceiling in expanding her business.

4.3 Glass Ceiling Has an Impact on Women Entrepreneur

After analysing the data from the interviews, glass ceiling does have an impact on women entrepreneur, specifically on how they carry themselves and how they manage their business. Their glass ceiling exposure is proven to have affected how they see themselves, as woman and entrepreneur, how they create policies and make decision for their business. Having previous exposure of glass ceiling, women entrepreneurs are found to be very determined and assertive, and in control of themselves. The awareness of glass ceiling due to their gender does not affect their motivation and spirit in terms of building and expanding their business. This is a consistent finding for the majority of the sample. It is also possible that due to glass ceiling exposure, these women entrepreneurs gained ‘experience’ in terms of handling any barriers in their business. Although they are aware that there are barriers, most of the women entrepreneurs have the approach of ‘seeing problem as a challenge, rather than a barrier’.

“I think it is very possible for women, if we are not strong, when faced by glass ceiling, we feel demotivated. For me, I do think glass ceiling exists, but it is still can be managed. It’s not so complicated.” – Respondent 04

“The more aware we are that it is a barrier, means that we have to find another way to resolve them, in order for our survival.” – Respondent 10

“For me, the drive to be successful is too strong, so I can’t... Mediocrity is not something I can accept in peace. I cannot be at peace with myself, knowing that I don’t put out the best of me...” – Respondent 07

Lastly, women entrepreneurs with prior exposure to glass ceiling tend to avoid male- dominated industries all together, choosing industries that are more gender-neutral or woman-friendly, like education. This also applies to recruiting. One woman stated that she will designate tasks and jobs to minimize the collusion on gender. However, this thinking is developed for women in lower profile businesses. The lack of support system can also affect their decision and perception regarding this matter. It is found that in female-dominated industries, like the small-medium enterprises (SMEs) in Indonesia where the majority of the drivers are women, it is unlikely that there are barriers that are based on gender.

4.4 The Relationship of Culture and Glass Ceiling

As themes of patriarchy and role of culture appear in the previous analysis, this section will be discussing how culture plays a role in glass ceiling. Here, culture explains the expanded definition of glass ceiling in Indonesian women entrepreneur. As explained in the previous section, many of the barriers and limitations for working women in Indonesia does not necessarily come from the structure or the politics of the company. Here, patriarchy and traditional gender roles plays a big part in why Indonesian women entrepreneurs have an expanded view of glass ceiling.

“Here's the thing, in America, Hillary Clinton was unable to become president, why? I think one of the reason was because glass ceiling. If that's what happening in America, what about Indonesia? Indonesia with its culture and expectation of women that they need to be in certain ways.” – Respondent 04

In their answer, Indonesian women entrepreneur shows that, either in their previous career or in their venture as an entrepreneur, that there is a gender inequality where men seem to be the preferred, hence creating the barrier for women to entry and participate. The answer comes in spectrums of intensity, ranging from bullying remarks of underestimation to total exclusion of women in the field, even by women in the top management. In Indonesia, not only are men dominating the society, women are allowing them to do so.

Family also plays a role in the understanding of traditional gender role for a woman, which later affects her understanding about glass ceiling too. For women entrepreneurs who are raised in a supportive family with no strict standards about traditional gender roles, they are able to thrive and see that they are free to go after their aspirations.

But for women entrepreneurs who is raised with the image that women should be a certain image, it affects their understanding as well. Also, not only the family that raised them, but also the family that they got married to have an impact. Again, the women entrepreneurs who stated that they are 'encouraged' to leave their career and fulfil their traditional duties are all Muslims. Religion also may have an impact in the understanding of their glass ceiling. Although the majority of the Muslim women entrepreneurs in the sample practice Islam moderately, a similar sentiment about their families or their spouse's families cannot be proven. Muslim women entrepreneurs in the sample made remarks like 'it is believed that our place is to serve the family' and that women should put their endeavour second, after family and their husband. Not acknowledging these roles first are seen as 'overstepping' the husband's power.

4.5 The Importance of Family Support for Women Entrepreneur

Transitioning to the idea of patriarchy and gender roles, it is necessary to highlight the importance of support for women entrepreneurs, whether it comes from their spouse or family. Having supportive spouses and family helps women in managing the pressure of society while running their business. The support may range from words of encouragement, pushing these women to pursue education to further add value to themselves, to lending a hand in running the gender roles that women has at home. Spouse support is highly valuable, especially for women entrepreneurs. In the data, there are two patterns that emerged on the source of support for the women entrepreneurs: the support from husband since they are partners, or copreneurs, and support from the husband who are not their business partner.

"When it comes to husband... Since this is our business, he supports me. Maybe it will be different when I'm working it all by myself, here is not in charge and did not participate. Maybe automatically, there will be conflict there." – Respondent 02

As for non-business partner husband, they also play a big role in how women entrepreneur balance their life. Many of them cited that there is a shift of how modern men approach fatherhood and being a husband, saying that their husbands are willing to take on domestic housework and child care. A progress of the past, many of the women entrepreneurs are noticing that the responsibility division is no longer too traditional. Their husbands are willing to take the day off from work to take care of the children, or when the women need to do a business trip outside of the city, the husband were assuring that it is not a problem. It is possible that a more egalitarian approach is accepted due to profile of the women entrepreneurs in the sample. All of them are urban society that grew up in urban cities of Indonesia.

5 Conclusion

Based on the findings, glass ceiling, seen as an umbrella term for barriers by Indonesian women entrepreneurs, has a role in shaping their leadership style, especially how they carry themselves in their business, also as a woman and an entrepreneur. Understanding that most of the women entrepreneurs in the sample has recognized and aware of their own glass ceiling and has broken through to liberate themselves, their experience of glass ceiling shaped them to position themselves strategically in their business to gain advantages as a woman, even with barriers. By reflecting on their experience of glass ceiling, Indonesian women entrepreneurs are able to acknowledge the importance of family support, especially from their spouse, and its role on helping them reach their goals in their business. Although impactful, glass ceiling was not the main motivation for the majority of these wome entrepreneurs to start a business. Many of them did not feel the 'push' towards entrepreneurialism due to hygiene factors, but more to the 'pull' factors of motivational intentions.

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